

SOCIAL AND EDUCATIONAL IMPACT OF ICT TRAINING FOR THE VISUALLY IMPAIRED STUDENTS IN BANGLADESH

Md. Shahrier Haider (Corresponding author)

Assistant Professor, Department of Special Education
Institute of Education and Research (IER)
University of Dhaka, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh

&

PhD Student,

Monash University, Clayton, VIC-3168, Australia

Rayhan ara Zaman

Lecturer, Institute of Education and Research (IER)
Syed Ismail Hossain Siraji Bhavan (1st floor)
University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh

Md. Hamidur Rahman Mollah

Senior Officer
Learning and Professional Development (LPD) Department
The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB)
Chartered Accountant Bhaban, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abstract:

The article explored current practices regarding the nature and scope of ICT training for the visually impaired (VI) students in Bangladesh. As well as, it illustrated the educational implications of the ICT training programs. Regarding this issue, contemporary thoughts and expectations of the visually impaired students and the training experts is also addressed. Furthermore, towards creating a barrier free access to information for the visually impaired in Bangladesh, globally used technologies to access information are also identified. Organizations and the professionals related to importing appropriate technology, distribution, training, supervision etc.; and the visually impaired students who are being trained were interviewed; parallel to these, document analysis was carried out to understand the current practices intensively. The study found that the number of ICT training institutions is very few in Bangladesh and most of them are in the capital. Though Visual Impaired students badly need ICT training the training programs continued in Bangladesh is not up to date and consistent with concurrent needs. The study also found that ICT training has a significant impact on education and social inclusion of the Visually Impaired People in Bangladesh.

Key words: Visual Impairment, Education, ICT Training, Influential factor, Social Inclusion

1. Introduction

Generally people who can't see are considered as person with Visual Impairment (VI). Defining Visual impairment is a contested as well as complex issue. However for the study, the researchers considered both low vision and total blindness as Visual Impairment. But those whose sight problems can be corrected by spectacles or contact lenses are not included in VI. For that reason people with irretrievable sight loss are called visually impaired (Miller-Keane Encyclopedia and Dictionary of Medicine, 2003). Blindness refers to a condition where a person suffers from any of the conditions: total absence of sight; or visual acuity not exceeding 6/60 or 20/200 (Snellen) in the better eye even

with correction lenses; or limitation of the field of vision subtending an angle of 20 degree or worse (Jonas and Mosby, 2005).

Low vision refers to one who has an impairment of visual functioning even after treatment, and/ or standard refractive correction, and has a visual acuity of less than 6/18 to light perception or a visual field of less than 10 degrees from the point of fixation, but who uses, or is potentially able to use, vision for the planning and/or execution of a task. (WHO, 1992)

Though VI people are an inseparable part of our society, but they are not provided with equal rights and opportunities. They have integrated in the society but far away from inclusion. They are deprived in every sector especially in education and job. As a result they are failing to prove themselves as a worth part of their family and society. But, education can help to change their life as education finds a way of earning which makes them empowered (Zaman & Haider, 2012) Now-a-days many visual impaired students are enrolled in schools and universities, but they are facing a lot of problems to continue their study smoothly. They are always lagging behind in their studies and failing to receive information as they are unable to read and write print materials. The number of braille books is limited and the limited braille books are not also available. So, VI students are suffering a lot. But, technology can fill the gap; it can alter the drawbacks into strength. A number of literatures (Haider, & Mollah, 2012; Rosenblum, Lewis, & D'Andrea, 2010; Evans, 2009; Presley & D'Andrea, 2009; Waldemar, Sekowski, & Brambring, 2006; Meister, 1998) showed persons with visual impairment now prefer newer technologies requiring auditory skills to make their life easier, while Braille material requires two to five times more time and effort than other assistive technologies, and thus dependency on modern ICT option were found increasingly popular worldwide. Having no sight is now a minor impairment which no longer can restrict a person to live his/her life at fullest, and which will not be otherwise possible with the Braille. But, the scenario of Bangladesh is different. The study attempts to find out the scopes of ICT options for visually impaired students and present practices of ICT for them in Bangladesh.

2. Objectives of the study

Visually Impaired people are using varieties of technologies worldwide to make their life smooth and easier. But, in Bangladesh ICT for VI is comparatively a new idea. The study aims to explore the picture of using ICT options, and nature and scope of ICT training programs for the visually impaired (VI) students in Bangladesh. Besides, it finds out the assistive technologies that are VI people are using worldwide. The article also intends to identify the influential factors of VI people for participating in the ICT training programs. Moreover, it aims to find out the educational implications of ICT training for the visually impaired students. Figure out the scopes of application of the achieved ICT skills in social life is another area of interest of the study.

3. Methodology

Since this study requires significant details through data collection two types of interview schedules which contained open ended questions were administered. Necessary attempts to ensure validity and reliability of the research contents were also followed. Trainers and trainees of ICT training centers for Visually Impaired students in Bangladesh were the respondents of the study. From Dhaka division, 10 organizations related to capacity building through ICT training for the Visual Impaired students were selected purposively. 40 trained visual impaired students and 10 professional trainers were interviewed. The extract from the interviewees was then compared and blend with the relevant secondary data to find the linkage and to denote the interrelation among the acting factors. The collected data was then processed and analyzed thematically with the focus of qualitative analysis and the findings, thus, presented thematically.

4. ICT for Visually Impaired students

About 15% of the total populations of the world are special needed people (WB& WHO, 2011), and 80% of the people with Special Educational Needs (SEN) live in developing countries (United Nations Enable, 2007).

People with visual impairment are a part of these Special Educational Needed (SEN) people whom are not small in number. There are 285 million Visual impaired in the world (IAPB, 2011). Ninety per cent of children with disabilities in developing countries do not attend school, says United Nations Enable (2007). Another statistics show, more than 50% of the SEN people are either illiterate or print disabled who are unable to read print materials. The statistics indicate it needs to think seriously on this issue (Bhattacharjee, 2008). Undoubtedly, it is a violation to their right to education and information as they cannot get much accessible information. Many of the visually impaired students are entering different educational institutions overcoming numerous barriers and trying to continue their studies. But, it is not easy for them as they are unable to read printed books and other written materials. Accessible information is also not available to them and thus their right to information is not recognized. Therefore, they are always lagging behind in their studies and receiving information. This creates an uneven competition for the print disabled and visually challenged.

However, there are a number of technical progresses all over the globe that can provide the print disabled and visually impaired people with accessible information systems and study materials which can enable them to equal access of information like the sighted people. Numerous studies found that worldwide Visually Impaired students started preferring the use of modern technology rather than Braille machines. D'Andrea (2010) identified a total of 25 devices as tools for classroom learning in high school and college among 16-22 years aged students. The 25 devices are showing in Table 1.

1. Braille Note	2. Cell phone with Mobile Speak
3. Book Port	4. Talking Calculator
5. Cassette tape player	6. Victor Reader
7. Braille Plus	8. Victor Stream
9. OCR scanner	10. Victor Wave
11. Books on tape	12. Victor Vibe
13. Computer with 'JAWS'	14. Perkins braille
15. Electronic Braille embosser	16. Braille label maker
17. Books on CD	18. Digital recorder
19. Computer with 'Window Eyes'	20. Computer with 'MAGIC'
21. Brilliant 24	22. GPS system
23. Large Print	24. Franklin Language Master
25. Electronic books from Book Share, RFB&D and Web Braille	

Table 1. Assistive technologies for Visually Impaired students (D'Andrea, 2010)

The above table consist of 25 names of assistive devices for Visually Impaired students. These devices help them in study and make social life easier. Among the devices Braille Note, Book Port, Cassette tape player, Books on tape, Perkins braille, Talking Calculator, Braille Plus etc. are mainly related to studies of VI students. Softwares like JAWS, MAGIC, Window eye are found to be very effective for them. Computers with these softwares give them access into the world of knowledge.

In many parts of the world NGOs are giving their efforts to avail the benefits of ICT for the visually impaired people. They arrange their ICT training programs for bringing the benefits of new technologies to disabled and other

disadvantaged communities. These ICT training approaches can be clustered into three broad categories – project-based, skills-based and industry-specific. The characteristics of the NGOs, the processes they follow to create ICT training programs and other practices differ according to these categories (Garrido, Coward, & Gordon, 2007).

Project-based ICT training is embedded within a locally relevant purpose and in the context of social issues. Industry-specific ICT training is the training in which ICT skills are tailored for specific sectors of the economy (tourism, legal services, health, etc.). Skills-based ICT training is stand-alone training on ICT applications without integrating any social purpose into the training. Its' main characteristics are:

1. Emphasis on mastery of skills
2. Especially relevant in urban areas and industrial zones where there is high multi-sector demand for workers with ICT skills; and
3. Importance of certification in ICT skills. (Garrido, Coward, & Gordon, 2007)

5. Present practice of ICT usage and training programs for Visually Impaired students in Bangladesh

With 53.7% functional literacy rate (GOB, 2011) and majority of population based in rural areas, people of Bangladesh predominantly rely on traditional and low-tech ICT options to have access to information. In the ICT Development Index released in 2010 by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU, 2010), rank of Bangladesh is not encouraging yet. Bangladesh is ranked 138, only above the Nepal, out of 154 countries. Besides that, public access to ICTs with or without internet connectivity during last one decade (2001-2010) mainly through private and non-profit initiatives, played an important role to enhance access to information, although it was not adequate proportionate to the needs (A2I, 2010). Information and communication technology (ICT) has become, within a very short time, one of the basic building blocks of modern society. Because, it plays an important role for educational, economic and social development. The people of Bangladesh are now getting the benefits of the ICT for their day to day life. But still, we are far behind in the high way of ICT. Especially visually impaired (VI) and the people living in the village are deprived of benefits of ICT.

4 million people are visually challenged in Bangladesh and numbers of visually impaired students are now studying at school and University Level; there is a severe lacking of adequate study materials and books for them both in market and libraries (Bhattacharjee, 2008). The class notes and lectures are a base of study at school and University level which is never at an accessible format for the visually challenged. But, technologies can ease the problems of visually impaired students. It is a matter of sorrow that most of the newer technologies are still unavailable in the country, while the available technologies are getting beyond the reach of grass root. Yet, some developmental organizations are trying to fill the gap and providing training for the students with visual impairment, in association with several organizations to enhance their access to information. Typically, the main component of such training programs is to acquaint VI students to Computer Screen reading software, speech synthesizers, self-voicing software, using Microsoft Word, Excel, PowerPoint with JAWS (Job Access with Speech), using DAISY (Digital Accessible Information System) Talking Book, Visually impairment friendly Electronic Books, Novels, Stories and different Policy and Legislations of Bangladesh (Technet, 2009).

In Bangladesh, ICT training means only computer training for visually impaired students. The number of training centers is limited and most of the centers based in the capital. As a result rural VI students fail to get ICT training or they bound to come in the capital where they face a huge housing, transportation and economic problem. The study observed ten institutions which are providing ICT training programs for visually impaired people. The ten

institutions were, Vocational Training Center for the Blind (VTCB), Center for Differently Able (CDA), Institute Of Hazrat Muhammad (Sm) (IHA), Bangladesh Organization For Disable Advancement (BODA), Bangladesh Visually Impaired People’s Society (BVIPS), Bangladesh Computer Council, Helen Keler International (HKI), Dhaka University, Baptist Mission Integrated School (BMIS) and Blind People’s Educational and Rehabilitational Development Organization (BERDO). These ten institutions are not an exception; also they are providing mainly computer training program for visually impaired. The training centers are mainly NGOs those are working for VI people are running ICT training program besides their main activities. Every training institute has 10 to 30 trainee students. The training centers have 3 to 10 computers and 1 or 2 trainers. Trainers are not skilled enough to provide quality training. The taught skills are limited in MS office applications and internet browsing. Though, in the developed countries VI people are doing very well in programming, freelancing and other technical areas of hardware and software; none of the Bangladeshi training centers are focusing on these topics. None of the institutions have modern curriculum and syllabus. Their training programs are traditional and stereotyped. Most of the programs are least effective for visually impaired trainees. In response to the question whether their target is achieved or not, 45% (18 out of 40) students said the aim attained as they can avail to use the learnt skills in study, communication, self -dependency and other sectors. 25% (10 out of 40) respondents expect their aim will attain in future when they will get jobs. 30% (12 out of 40) informed their training aim didn’t fulfill as they don’t have PC or the program was unsuccessful for other reasons. The length of the training programs varies from 10 days to 9 months. Training centers do not take any tuition fees. Moreover, each of the training centers gives a little amount of transport allowances to all the trainees. Besides computer training few organizations also provide PABX training. 50% of the respondents (20 out of 40) received PABX training besides computer training.

6. Influential factors for the VI students to participate in ICT training

This is the modern age of technologies and ICT is an inseparable part of this modern life. Development is not possible without technological knowledge. This is also true for visually impaired person. To integrate in the modern world many visually impaired students (22.5%) are taking ICT training. They believe the computer training will help them for social inclusion, help to reduce the degree of disability and make them more independent. Another and the greatest influential factor for visually impaired people to participate in ICT training was job sector which offers a lot of opportunities. 55% of the trainee respondents and 60% of the trainers believe that the possibility of getting job increases if a visual impaired person has computer training. Technology helps to make life easier which is another alternative point. It is a means of communication and entertainment. Some were participated to make them more competent and will be able to use the technology in day to day life. (See Chart 1)

Figure 1. Opinion of trainers and trainees about Influencing factors of ICT training (One respondent identified more than one option)

The study also found that technology also reduces academic barriers of visually impaired students. For this reason, it is another influencing factor according to 40% trainers and trainees. They mentioned that it is also helpful in reducing dependency as it allows reading and writing independently.

7. Using ICT in educational perspective

From primary to higher education a number of VI students are studying in the mainstream education. Braille and audio books are not sufficient to their demands. Text books, handouts, guidebooks and question papers are always found in printed format which Visually Impaired students cannot easily accessed. Educational technologies are working to fill this gap though they are small in number. Many of the VI students are using different technologies as a helping hand for education. The study found that 45% respondents (18 out of 40) use computer in academic perspective, 27.5% mentioned about MP3 or Walkman or cassette player. Most of the students(65%) use recorder (a little number of students are allowed to use tape recorder in the classroom),60% use Braille, 27.5% use mobile and 5% use other technologies in academic perspective. 5% respondents said they don't use any technologies for academic perspective.

The interviewed trainers informed visually impaired students don't use many technologies in academic perspective. Most of them use recorder and cassette players. 70% of the trainers identified recorders as the main used technology by visually impaired student. 50% informed about computer, 20% of the trainers identified mobile; 10% named PDA and other technologies, 20% said braille and another 10% said visually impaired students don't use any technologies for educational help. (See chart 2)

Figure 2: Percentage of used technologies in academic perspective

8. Using ICT in social perspective

Most of the visually impaired people are not getting the opportunity to use technology in their daily life. A few of them who are enjoying the blessing of ICT in real life were very happy with it. Because it is a source of entertainment, way of communication, source of information, medium of reducing dependency, way of making awareness and means of office management. 22.5% of the respondents use the technology in their real life for

entertainment. Communication is also a sector where visually impaired trainees are applying their knowledge and skills. Technology is very helpful in educational matters. Many of them are continuing their studies with less difficulty and making good results. 37.5% trainees (15 out of 40) inform that their educational life is blessed with computer. They are now able to make a good result in academic exams. Employment sectors create huge opportunities for these people. ICT training, it makes them self-dependent and equally contributing member in the family in real life. 7.5% agreed, the training are helping them in job sectors and another 7.5% of the respondents are using the training skills in accomplishing their personal works. 71.5% of the respondents are using the skills in different purposes and 32.5% informed that ICT is not helping them in their real life.

9. Conclusion

A visually impaired can be blessed in all aspects of life by using ICT. ICT helps to continue their study, communication, entertainment, job and other works of daily life facing less difficulty. But most of the visually impaired people of Bangladesh are not aware of the benefits of ICT options. Besides, who are participating in the training programs, are not getting enough opportunity to use technologies in real life. Moreover technologies are not available for visually impaired in Bangladesh. Computers are expensive and visually impaired friendly software is not available; and some software which they are using is pirated one. Besides, talking software supportive mobile, talking watch, money identifier device, mobility device like third eye and different types of low vision aids are needed to make available also. Making ICT options available and reducing their price or making those cheaper especially for visually impaired may be a solution. Enhancing and patronizing ICT options for Visually Impaired obviously will help to make their life easier, beautiful and enjoyable.

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